

THE ROLE OF LIBRARY INFORMATION RESOURCES AND SERVICES IN PROMOTING ENTREPRENEURSHIP EDUCATION AND SKILL ACQUISITION AMONG STUDENTS IN POLYTECHNIC IN BENUE STATE

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Abstract

The study examined the role of library information resources and services for promoting entrepreneurship education for skill acquisition. The study was carried out on students in polytechnics in Benue state. The study adopted a survey design, the total sample size of three hundred (300) questionnaires out of which 285 duly were completed and returned. A purposive sampling technique was used to select final-year students from each institution. Data was collected through structured questionnaires. Responses were recorded on a four-point Likert scale (Strongly Agree, Agree, Disagree, Strongly Disagree). The data was analyzed using descriptive statistics (percentages and frequency distributions). A mean score of 2.5 serve as the benchmark for interpreting responses scores above, 2.5 indicate agreement, while those below 2.5 indicate disagreement. Descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation was used to analyze results. The findings shows that while polytechnic libraries offer a variety of relevant information resources, challenges such as obsolete information resources, inadequate funding, limited technology, and poor services hinder their full potential of the library. The study therefore recommends increasing library funding, investing in technology, expanding library space, enhancing staff training for effective services delivery and regularly updating entrepreneurship-related resources.

Introduction

Entrepreneurship is a key to economic and development process in Nigerian and the whole world at large. Entrepreneurship is best understood as competency on resourceful skills capable of steering individual to self-reliance, independent and productive citizen. According to Bectseh and Ahima (2012) entrepreneurship

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harnesses the interests and innate potential of an individual, prevents wastes of human resources and serves as alternative in the absence of government structured-employment (white collar job). In view of this, it becomes much necessary for tertiary institution most especially institution like polytechnics to have courses of entrepreneurship education. For any graduating student to be self-reliant, such a student must acquire the right habits, attitudes, saleable skill and motivational skill acquisition through entrepreneurship education.

The introduction of entrepreneurship education by the federal government of Nigerian and its adoption by the National Board for Technical Education (NBTE) syllabus is a concrete effort to stem the tide of rising graduate unemployment in the country. Bako, Taiwo, Mohammed and Olopade (2021) stated that the recent inclusion of Entrepreneurship Education in tertiary educational institutions in Nigeria is an indication of its importance to employment creation; as Nigeria continues to turn out graduates from our various institutions that are hardly self-reliant but solely dependent on white collar jobs for sustenance because they lack adequate skills that will make them function effectively. Nnadozie, Akanwa and Nnadozie (2013) noted that one of the aftermaths of the ongoing curriculum innovation in Nigeria polytechnic sector is the introduction of entrepreneurship education in all programmes/disciplines. Anyanron, Obichere and Ossai-Onah (2012) stated that entrepreneurship education is the process of inculcating the knowledge of creating value by pooling together a unique package of resources to exploit an opportunity conceptualized entrepreneurship education if implemented in Nigeria tertiary education. According to international standard it will equip the undergraduate with business skills that would make students self-employed after graduation rather than job seekers. Bectsh and Ahima (2012) see entrepreneurship education as playing a role in the process of economic development through creation of employment, increase investment and consumption of a nation. Thus, the entrepreneurial education acquire lead to skill acquisition.

To align the success of entrepreneurship education for skill acquisition, it is much necessary to have a formidable library that provide adequate information resource and services to promote the activities of entrepreneurship education in polytechnics, skill acquisition is acquire mostly through entrepreneurship education. To adequately become skillful, it is necessary that student takes the advantage of using the library to discover new knowledge; Onyedikachi (2018) see libraries as institution responsible for collecting, processing and storing recorded knowledge for the purpose of reading, study and consultation. Library plays a vital role in equipping users with the knowledge and skill needed to be innovative, library empower users to be catalysts for positive change. Opele and Adigun (2023) stated that the library serves as information hubs, promote lifelong learning, support innovation, and contribute to the overall development of individuals and the nation as a whole. Besides, the library plays a multifaceted role in the nation's educational landscape. Hence, by students prioritizing library, Nigeria can build a knowledge-based society that thrives on the power of information and embraces lifelong learning (Kaur et al., 2018).

Library information resources and services are provided to serve and support education activities of an institution, every library depends on availability of information resource and services to users. In order to understand the effectiveness and efficiency on the use of library information resources and services, the research need to evaluate the performance role and activities of libraries information resources in promoting entrepreneurship education and skill acquisition among polytechnic students.

Statement of the Problem

In Nigeria, there is a rising problem of under employment resulting to poverty and all forms of social evils. Bugaje (2023) noted that despite the enormous resources of Nigeria, the nation is facing daunting socio-economic challenges which must be addressed to avoid the bubble collapsing. The key underlying symptom of

these challenges is unemployment. The ironic joblessness in the midst of plenty of jobs from many infrastructural projects is because of the absence of relevant information resources for entrepreneurship education and skill acquisition.

The role of library information resources and services in promoting entrepreneurship education has been viewed to be critical to the overall development of a nation. Library enhance critical thinking skills, foster a love for reading, and empower individuals to become self-develop and lifelong learners (Khan et al., 2022).

However, from observation most of the polytechnic libraries are not adequately funded to provide the needed information resources and services to promote self-skill acquisition and entrepreneurship education. Also, the absent of current and relevant information resources affect the services render in the library. It is against this background the research intends to investigate the role of library information resources and services in promoting entrepreneurship education and skill acquisition among Polytechnic students in Benue state polytechnic.

Objective(s) of the Study:

The general objective of this study is to appraise the role of information resources and services in promoting entrepreneurship education and skill acquisition among polytechnic students. The specific objectives are to:

- (1) Find out the availability of information resources for promoting entrepreneurship and skill acquisition in the polytechnic libraries in Benue state.
- (2) Determine the relevancy and currency of the information resources for promoting entrepreneurship and skill acquisition in the polytechnic libraries in Benue state.
- (3) Find out the constrain factors in providing library information resources services for promoting entrepreneurship education for skill acquisition in the polytechnic libraries in Benue state.

Literature Review

Libraries are custodian and repository of knowledge. The library had been positioned as a veritable and positive impact factor in the achievement of education. Libraries are important institution, that promotes national economic and industrial development in Nigeria, but lack of awareness of the importance of libraries can result to less knowledge in area of study. Libraries had also been seen to have a role in policy for all-inclusive education programmes for information literacy and life-long learning as well as information provisions for entrepreneurship education for skill acquisition but the biggest challenge these days is the paradigm shift from employee mindset to entrepreneur mindset. it is necessary to encourage polytechnic students to endeavor to embrace and use the provided information resources for entrepreneurship education to acquire a skill in a specific area of interest. Traditionally graduate of high learning mostly develop interest in structured employment rather the self-acquire skill employment. They often find it difficult to develop a positive attitude toward entrepreneurship. According to Chinwe and Ugwa (2013) it must be emphasized that training programmes are required to improve student's skills in their various area of academic specialization. However, inadequate entrepreneurship curricular and facilities and motivational library materials in higher institutions is the challenge.

Entrepreneurship education and skill acquisition which is an essential ingredient for success in entrepreneurship should be strengthened and sustained by directing student to library to read more to acquire other people's experience and skill. In this regard, use of library as a course should be restructured and articulated to accommodate entrepreneurial studies not only as a general course, but also as a departmental course to take care of the managerial and professional components of entrepreneurship respectively. As such, it has become necessary for the libraries to retool and re-equip the library with relevant and current information resources and

services in order to promote its use and make students active participants in order to strike a balance between theory and practice. Odufuwa (2012) noted the essence of tertiary education is to endow students with basic skills they would need to perform in any situation and advocate for additional skills outside the course of study in order to widen the students' horizon and opportunities of acquiring new skills. To address this, the authorities of the institution should provide adequate funds for libraries to acquire all necessary information resources that will encourage and promote the use of library resources for formidable skill acquisition. Skill acquisitions have been considered as the brain behind entrepreneurship education and development in Nigeria. Bako, Taiwo, Mohammed and Olopade (2021) opine that skill acquisition is a process to obtain new ideas and knowledge over time to enhance one's understanding and application of concepts.

Skill acquisition is a basic ability that a man can acquire and adjust to life. Etonyeaku et al (2018) opine that skill is the capacity of a person to accomplish a task within desired precision and certainty. Skill involves a practical knowledge in combination with clearness, expertise, dexterity and ability to perform a function which could be acquired or learnt in school or training centers through learning experience. Therefore, entrepreneurial skill acquisition is said to be a necessary set of skills required to be an entrepreneur. In other words, entrepreneurial skill acquisition are those necessary skills an entrepreneur needs to successfully run business or add value at work. Agu, Chiahah and Ikime (2013) agreed that acquisition skills must be nurtured through proper education so that it can be directed to enriching small business endeavors that will benefit the individuals and the communities in which entrepreneurs live.

Nigerian tertiary institutions produce millions of graduates annually into an economy which is already overpopulated, thereby raising the level of unemployment. It is on the note that the government in conjunction with the agencies tend to introduce skill acquisition programmes in order to correct the anomaly and ensure that these newly graduated students become self-reliant and prepare for a future which in turn devoids the economy of miscreants. Hence, researchers seek to identify library roles in promoting entrepreneurship and skill acquisition through library collection and services rendered.

Theoretical Framework

To strengthen the findings of this research work, two theories were: psychological theory and theory of entrepreneur were used:

Psychological theory by Refugee and Schumpeter which stated that, the ability to make good judgment about the future leads an individual to become a successful entrepreneur. According to Islam (1989) psychological theory is presumed mechanism by which achievement level translates itself into economic growth in the entrepreneurial class. If the need for achievement is high, there will be more people who behave like entrepreneurs.

While, the theory of entrepreneur by David McClelland, stresses that an entrepreneur works in a structured and creative way which eventually leads to better decision making in predicaments. The theory also stated that traits of entrepreneurship are incorporated by individuals through learning and this learning can be motivate them to achieve a higher level.

Methodology

This study used a survey research design to explore how library information resources and services support entrepreneurship education for skill acquisition in three selected polytechnics in Benue State: Federal Polytechnic Wannune, Akpaeran Orshin Polytechnic, and Benue State Polytechnic Ugbokolo. The focus was on final-year students (ND & HND), as they are the key users of these resources. A total of 300 questionnaires were distributed out of which 285 were duly completed and returned. To ensure fairness, a purposive sampling

technique was used to select participants, followed by a simple random sampling method (balloting) to pick up of final-year students from each institution. Data was collected through a structured questionnaire. Responses were recorded based on a four-point Likert scale (Strongly Agree to Strongly Disagree). The data was analyzed using descriptive statistics (percentages and frequency distributions). A mean score of 2.5 will serve as the benchmark for interpreting responses—scores above 2.5 will indicate agreement, while those below 2.5 will indicate disagreement. Descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation was used to analyze research questions

Data Analysis and Discussions

Demographic Information will be provided in the table below. Each of the items was rated in frequencies and percentages.

Category	Frequency	Percentage
Institution		
Benue State Polytechnic, Ugbokolo	113	37.6%
Akpaeran Orshin Polytechnic	106	35.3%
Federal Polytechnic, Wannune	66	22%
Gender		
Male	171	60%
Female	114	40%
Program of Study		
National Diploma (ND)	160	56%
Higher National Diploma (HND)	125	44%

The demographic information of respondents provides valuable insights into the composition of students who participated in this study. A total of 300 students were given questionnaires, but only 95% (285 students) successfully returned them. This response rate indicates a high level of participation and interest in the study while acknowledging a 5% non-response rate that may be attributed to factors such as improper computation of questionnaires, or lack of interest. Among the responding students, the distribution across institutions shows that Benue State Polytechnic, Ugbokolo had the highest representation with 37.6% (113 respondents), followed by Akpaeran Orshin Polytechnic with 35.3% (106 respondents), and Federal Polytechnic, Wannune with 22% (66 respondents). The difference in institutional representation may reflect variations in student population sizes, engagement levels, or institutional factors influencing participation in the study. The gender distribution of respondents reveals that male students (171, 60%) were more represented than female students (114, 40%). This suggests a potential gender gap in student enrollment or participation in the programs under study. Regarding the academic level of respondents, 56% (160 students) were enrolled in the National Diploma (ND) program, while 44% (125 students) were in the Higher National Diploma (HND) program. This reflects the typical structure of polytechnic education, where ND programs generally have higher enrollment numbers as they serve as the entry-level qualification before students' progress to HND. Additionally, the study focused solely on students, with all 285 respondents (100%) being students, as library staff were excluded from the analysis. This ensures that the findings are directly relevant to understanding student perspectives on the role of library resources in entrepreneurship education and skill acquisition.

Table 1: Availability of Information Resources and Services

The data on the availability of information resources and services in the library to support entrepreneurship education and skill acquisition. The table highlights respondents' perceptions regarding the adequacy of materials, access to both physical and digital resources, and the library's efforts in acquiring new materials and services. The mean values indicate the general trend of agreement or disagreement with each statement, while the standard deviation reflects the variability in responses."

S/N	Statement	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	Standard Deviation
1	The library has a wide range of materials (books, journals, e-resources) to support entrepreneurship education.	51	19	117	98	2.00	0.85
2	The library has sufficient resources to support entrepreneurship related to skill acquisition.	48	29	95	113	2.05	0.89
3	The library provides access to both physical and digital resources that promote entrepreneurship education.	40	45	110	90	2.05	0.86
4	The library regularly acquires new materials to support entrepreneurship and skill acquisition.	97	113	38	37	3.10	0.78
5	There are adequate copies of essential entrepreneurship-related resources in the library to meet students' demands.	35	44	85	121	2.15	0.88

The above table 1 findings suggest that polytechnic libraries in Benue State, Nigeria, are not well-equipped to support entrepreneurship education and skill acquisition. Many students feel the libraries lack a sufficient range of books, journals, and e-resources, as seen in the low mean score (**2.00**, SD = 0.85). Similarly, resources for skill acquisition are also inadequate (**2.05**, SD = 0.89), aligning with studies that highlight resource shortages in Nigerian academic libraries (Ogbomo & Idiodi, 2021). Access to both physical and digital entrepreneurship materials is also limited (**2.05**, SD = 0.86), which is concerning as digital resources are vital for staying updated with global trends (Eze & Uzoigwe, 2020). Many polytechnic libraries still struggle with poor infrastructure and insufficient funding for digital collections. However, students acknowledged that new materials are occasionally acquired (**3.10**, SD = 0.78), though without structured acquisition policies, these efforts may not be impactful (Aina, 2019). Another challenge is the insufficient copies of key entrepreneurship resources (**2.15**, SD = 0.88), making access difficult for students. This aligns with research showing that a lack of essential textbooks in Nigerian libraries hinders effective learning (Yusuf & Iwu, 2018). While some progress has been made, polytechnic libraries must prioritize acquiring relevant materials, increasing digital resources, and ensuring multiple copies of key books are available.

Table 2: Relevance and Currency of Information Resources: highlights how respondents perceive the relevance and up-to-date of the library's resources for entrepreneurship education. It explores whether the materials available both digital and print are current, reflect the latest trends, and effectively support students' learning needs. The mean scores give an idea of the general agreement among respondents, while the standard deviation shows how varied their opinions are.

S/N	Statement	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	Standard Deviation
1	The library provides up-to-date resources related to entrepreneurship education.	34	36	114	101	2.05	0.87
2	The library's resources reflect the latest trends and developments in entrepreneurship.	38	41	113	93	2.10	0.86
3	The entrepreneurship e-resources in the library are mostly current and relevant.	40	47	115	83	2.89	0.81
4	Information resources are mostly current and relevant (such as books, journals etc).	55	25	89	116	2.08	0.88
5	The resources available in the library for entrepreneurship education are relevant	30	35	118	102	2.01	0.88

The findings in Table 2 suggest that polytechnic libraries in Benue State struggle to provide up-to-date and relevant resources for entrepreneurship education. Many students feel that the library does not offer current materials, as shown by the low mean score (**2.05**, SD = 0.87) for the statement on the availability of up-to-date resources. Similarly, students do not believe the library's resources reflect the latest trends in entrepreneurship (**2.10**, SD = 0.86), indicating that the collection may be outdated and insufficient for contemporary entrepreneurial learning.

A slightly better response was recorded for current and relevant e-resources, with a mean score of **2.89** (SD = 0.81). This suggests that while digital resources exist, they may not be comprehensive or widely accessible to all students. However, when considering physical materials like books and journals, the mean score dropped to **2.08** (SD = 0.88), further reinforcing concerns about the relevance and timeliness of library collections. Additionally, the overall relevance of library resources for entrepreneurship education received a low mean score (**2.01**, SD = 0.88), suggesting that students do not find the available materials useful for their learning needs.

These findings align with previous research indicating that many academic libraries in Nigeria struggle to update their collections regularly due to financial and infrastructural constraints (Ogbomo & Idiodi, 2021). The lack of current resources can negatively impact students' ability to stay informed about modern entrepreneurial practices and trends (Eze & Uzoigwe, 2020).

Table 3: Challenges in Providing Information Resources and Services

S/N	Statement	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	Standard Deviation
1	Inadequate funding for new resources for entrepreneurship education.	121	95	30	39	3.04	0.85
2	There is a lack of current and relevant materials for entrepreneurship education in the library.	119	93	45	28	3.06	0.80
3	The library lacks adequate computers to support entrepreneurship education, such as e-books or online databases.	111	107	33	34	3.03	0.82
4	There library services to effectively support students in accessing entrepreneurship resources.	115	88	50	32	2.98	0.83
5	Limited access to digital resources (e.g., internet or e-books) is a challenge for students pursuing entrepreneurship education.	94	111	45	35	2.94	0.84

Table 3: Discussion of Findings

The findings reveal significant challenges affecting the provision of library resources and services for entrepreneurship education. Inadequate funding emerged as a major issue, with mean = 3.04 of respondents agreeing that the library lacks sufficient financial support for acquiring new materials. This is consistent with Aguolu and Aguolu (2019), who emphasized that underfunding remains a major constraint in Nigerian academic libraries.

A lack of current and relevant materials was also highlighted, with a mean score of 3.06 agreement, indicating that many of the resources in the library may be outdated or insufficient to meet students' entrepreneurship learning needs (Ekere et al., 2020). This can hinder students' ability to gain updated knowledge on entrepreneurship trends and innovations (Omeluzor & Oyovwe-Tinuoye, 2021). The lack of adequate computers and digital infrastructure was another key challenge, with mean = 3.03 agreeing that there are insufficient e-books and online databases. This supports the findings of Edem & Egbe (2019), who noted that many Nigerian polytechnic libraries lack sufficient ICT resources for effective digital learning. Similarly, a shortage of inadequate services in the library was identified as a barrier, with a mean score of 2.98 agreement. This suggests that students may not be receiving adequate guidance on accessing and utilizing entrepreneurship-related resources (Ogbomo & Balarabe, 2022). In addition, limited access to digital resources, such as e-books and internet services, was acknowledged by mean = 2.94. This aligns with Aina (2020), who argued that the digital divide and poor internet connectivity significantly impact students' access to online learning materials.

General, these findings suggest that funding constraints, outdated resources, lack of ICT facilities, inadequate services shortages, and limited digital access are key barriers to effective entrepreneurship education support in the library. Addressing these challenges through increased investment, ICT integration, and improved services would enhance the library's ability to support students in acquiring entrepreneurship skills.

Conclusion:

The research explores the role of library resources and services in promoting entrepreneurship education and skill development among polytechnic students in Benue State. It finds that libraries provide a good range of relevant resources, including books, journals, and digital content, but faces challenges such as insufficient funding, obsolete books and journals outdated technology, and poor services. These issues hinder libraries' ability to fully support entrepreneurship education. Despite these challenges, libraries are recognized as vital in fostering entrepreneurial skills and helping students become more self-reliant and better prepared for entrepreneurial success.

Recommendations: Based on the findings of this study on the role of information resources and services in promoting entrepreneurship education and skill acquisition among polytechnic students in Benue State, the following recommendations are made:

1. **Improve the Availability of Information Resources,** Polytechnic libraries should acquire more books, journals, and electronic resources related to entrepreneurship and skill acquisition. Ensuring multiple copies of essential materials and partnering with organizations for additional resources will help meet students' demands.
2. **Ensure the Relevance and Currency of Resources,** Libraries should regularly update their collections to reflect current entrepreneurship trends. Strengthening subscriptions to online databases and conducting periodic reviews will help align library materials with industry developments.
3. **Address Constraints in Providing Library Information Resources and Services,** Increased funding should be sought to improve resource acquisition and service delivery. Investments in digital

infrastructure and staff training on entrepreneurship-related information services will enhance accessibility and usage of library resources.

By addressing these issues, polytechnic libraries in Benue State can better support entrepreneurship education and foster skill acquisition, ultimately contributing to the development of self-reliant graduates who are equipped to thrive in a dynamic and challenging economic environment.

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